

LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES IN SPECIALIZED TRANSLATION AND TERMINOLOGY: THE CHALLENGES OF TRANSLATION OF MEDICAL TERMS

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Annotation: There are some linguistic challenges some translators and interpreters might have within translation and interpretation of medical terms as Greek and Latin languages are normally used in the medical sphere. In the article some translation methods are investigated and suggested to translators developing in interpretation medical texts.

Key words: medical terminology, translation method, medical terms, medical abbreviations, Greek, Latin, ‘false friends’.

Medical terminology is defined to have the international character and contain a great deal of terms depending on the medical areas they are used such as anatomical, histological and clinical.

Simultaneously, according to Guba (2019), medical terminology is peculiar with the use of terms of Greek and Latin origin and also the presence of synonyms which might be translated incorrectly. And there are also such terms the meaning of which is possible to translate only taking into consideration contextual information. Another challenge might be revealed with the help of differences of English and Latin terms with the use of Greek words correspondingly. E.g. is kidney (English) – ren (Latin) – nephros (Greek).

Medical texts own the diversity of abbreviations and special terms, technical instructions to medical equipment which makes translators have not only medical knowledge but also be aware in technical sphere.

Knowing about the fact that Greek and Latin words are used in medical terminology, it should be essential to know about existence of 'false friends'. They might be called the main challenge of translation as two words in two languages can have the same pronunciation and writing, but different meaning. For example, the word 'symptomatic' has both the direct meaning and the meaning of 'clinical'. However, 'symptomatic therapy' has only the direct translation. (Guba, 2019)

'False friends' might not only change the meaning, but also confuse the translator. For instance, the disease 'mucoviscidosis' in some sources might be presented as 'cystic fibrosis' which in its turn is another illness. In such cases, it is necessary for translators to check whether such a term exists and whether it is translated correctly. It should be remembered by translators that words can change their meaning depending on the sphere of use or even have the traits of professionalisms. If there is a case, translators can make additions, deletions and descriptions for such terms.

Distinguishing dictionary coincidences is the most common translating type of terms. The constant accordance is the most persistent method of translation of units of original language. It is used in all or almost in all cases. Equivalent language units are known as the language units whose content does not depend on the contextual information. As an equivalent language unit, the word does not require to search for analogues or synonyms and can be translated transferring the fullest accuracy in translation.

According to Komissarov (2013) the constant accordance can be noticed among professionalisms, people's names, toponyms, and some phrases and expressions which are used in daily speech. For example, California, San Francisco, Neuropsychiatrist, medical history, lab test, symptom, coronary arteries.

Another method of translation is transcription. It is the type of translation at which the sound form of English words is transited with the letters of the translated language. For example, the word 'dentrit' has the same pronunciation in Russian as well. However, with the difference in sounding and pronunciation of some letters in Russian and English, transcription is used not so often and as usual, might have differences in pronunciation.

Transliteration is also one of the common methods of translation in medical sphere. It proposes to transmit the word by letters from the original language into translated one. For example, the word 'organ' is transmitted into Russian with the same letters but pronunciation.

Calque translation is another method of translation; the translation is realized via replacement the original language unit with its lexical accordance in translated language. Calque translation might help to create a new language unit which copies

the structure of original language unit in details. Therefore, literal translation is fulfilled with the help of searching and applying the first equivalent word in the dictionary. As usual, calque translation is used when derivatives, compound words are needed to be translated. For example, such expressions as ‘molecular level’ or ‘lymphatic system’ are translated into Russian with the same consequence and meaning as in English.

Descriptive method is the translation of new terms of the original language in which the word, phrase or phraseological unit might be replaced with the expression transferring the meaning of the term adequately. Description is used in the cases when other methods are unapplicable. Simultaneously, the description should correspond some requirements: the translation should reflect the content of the notion as accurately as possible; the description should not be too detailed and syntactical structure of the translation should not be complicated and incomprehensive. (Zholos &Shevchenko, 2019)

A very interesting example of descriptive translation method is applied to such a disease which is called ‘the infectious disease’. However, in the Russian language the disease was named after the great Russian scientist, Sergey Petrovich Botkin (1832-1889), the Botkin’s disease. It is seen that the eponym in the Russian language does not have the same equivalent in English. Nevertheless, in the Latin language the disease is called ‘morbus Botkini’. Therefore, the mentioned eponym is applied internationally and used omnipresently in medical practice of diverse countries of the world. Zholos (2020) pointed that the main problem of eponyms is that they are strongly influenced by national specificity in their translation and absence of equivalents in other languages impacts their use and search for adequate descriptions.

Contextual replacement is used in the cases when the translated equivalent does not suit a dictionary meaning. In some cases, the deviation in translation is essential for comprehension as in different languages different translation rules and norms might be major. For instance, the word ‘anatomical’ might be translated not only directly, but also as ‘structural atom’ owing to traditional norms of the Russian Language there is a complex term which fulfills structurally functional relationship. (Bazylev, 2005)

In addition, metaphorical terms should be mentioned. Shevchenko (2018) states that metaphorical terms are such words and word phrases which are used in connotative meaning. Metaphorization of medical terms both in Russian and English often coincides and a number of metaphors have the same meaning in two languages. Nowadays, there is such a tendency to save metaphorical imagery of medical terms in translation from English into Russian.

Abbreviations and acronyms also play a significant role in translation methods. The English language has such peculiarities as compression, simplification of grammar structures and economy of language means. It is proven that a great deal of abbreviations is appearing in the English language in medical sphere which can

create new challenges for translators. To translate abbreviations the translator should be aware of their rapid adaptation in the English language and emerged controversies of the language system. Therefore, the challenge of translation of acronyms might appear. It is essential that accuracy and unambiguity of translation is reached. Because of wrong translation there are some patients who can suffer after wrong interpretation of an abbreviation of a medical term. According to Solntsev (2010) some linguists mention that abbreviations are inherent to the English language meanwhile, the Russian language does not have such a tendency.

In conclusion it can be said that the translation of medical terms is realized in different ways. The most common method is the search of dictionary accordance in target language. It is used in all or almost in all cases. However, some discrepancies in grammar, syntactical and morphological structures of the Russian and English languages make the translators use different transformation methods for an accurate interpretation of medical terms. They are: transcription, calque translation, descriptive method, contextual replacement, lexical addition.

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